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Bangsamoro Athletes' Hope and Desire

To win in different sports competitions, athletes should have rigid trainings and practice in their own field of sports, the presence of standard and quality sports equipment and facilities with the guidance of sports professionals are valuable. Ever since, the lack of standard and quality sport equipment and facilities around the BARMM Region is one of the reasons why Bangsamoro athletes failed to advance or even win in the yearly competition in Palarong Pambansa in the country. In fact, there are many capable sports enthusiasts and professionals who are willing to teach, guide and train student athletes but because of the absence of the quality and standard sports equipment and facilities make them not to pursue.

Less support to both student athletes and coaches in their trainings by the proper authorities make them less also. Bangsamoro athletes and coaches are seeking for immediate attention and help. They need support for them to produce more quality athletes in the region who can manage to reach and compete in the international arena.

The goal to win reflects dedication and determination of supporting bodies to provide the necessary equipment, facilities and financial support to these people. Let's start investing quality services towards Bangsamoro people especially the youth who believed to be the hope of our fatherland. Bangsamoro athletes will win if the authorities will choose to help and support them in their fight. Let's unite and cooperate in helping and supporting the Bangsamoro athletes in raising our flag not just in the national competition but also in international stage.